

Flower Blooms within Her : An Eco-feminine Study of the Endangered Races

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**Aryaputri
Sthitapragyan**
Lecturer
Department Of English
Ravenshaw University
CuttackOdisha, India

Abstract

The term ecology is defined as the interaction between living organisms and their environment. It primarily focuses on understanding how organisms including plants, animals and microorganisms interact with each other and with their physical surroundings. It also inspects how these interactions influence the distribution abundance of organisms, the functioning of the ecosystem and the flow of energy and nutrients through the environment. Likewise Eco-criticism is an interdisciplinary field of study that examines the relationship between literature and the environment.

Keywords

Flower Blooms,Eco-feminine,Endangered Races

Introduction

Eco criticism is known as environmental criticism. It focuses on the relationship between literature and the environment. It explores how the human and non-human entities are interconnected. How this interconnectedness affected our environment. In the current scenario eco criticism is highly significant to raise awareness about environmental sustainability. This eco criticism provides deeper understanding of the world out there and inspires sustainable practices.

It discusses how nature, ecology and environmental issues are represented in literature as well as how literature works with the natural world. It inspires issues through the lens of cultural and intellectual analysis of cultural advice for greater environmental awareness and action. Eco-feminism is a philosophical and social movement that amalgamate elements of feminism and environmentalism. It scrutinizes the connection between the exploitation of women and nature, indicating they both are linked by systems of dominion such as- patriarchy, capitalism and colonialism. They proclaimed that the same attitude that leads to the marginalization of women also assigns to the degradation of the environment.

Among several foreign ecofeminism one very popular activist is Vandana Shiva, known for her work *Staying Alive, Women, Ecology and Development*. In this book the writer is talking about the oppression of women and Exploitation of nature is highly interconnected.

Here the author argues that the traditional ecological knowledge, after held by women is essential for sustainable development. The primary focus of this book is the importance of biodiversity and the roles of women play in ecological resilience. In the book *Earth Democracy: Justice, Sustainability and Peace*, published in 2005 is another vision to globalisation which is rooted in ecological sustainability and social justice. This focuses on the principle of diversity, local economies and participatory democracy. The author evaluates corporate globalisation for its role in ecological destruction, inequality and cultural homogenisation. This book offers pathways for communication to reclaim sovereignty over their resources, food system and environments. When it comes to feminist eco criticism, this combines feminist theory and eco criticism and it explores the relationship between gender, environment and literature. This theory aims to examine how the patriarchal society has exploited both women and the natural world. It aims to promote a more inclusive and sustainable relationship between gender, environment and literature. Multiple books have been written on these ideas.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to study about the eco-feminism of the endangered races in "Flower Blooms within Her".

Review of Literature

Writers like Margaret Atwood, Alice Walker have examined ecological degradation, sustainability and the interconnections of humans with nature.

The book *The Death of Nature: Women, Ecology and the Scientific Revolution*, published in the year 1980 by Carolyn Merchant. This book focuses on the historical relationship between the scientific revolution and the changing perception of nature, focusing on how these ideas contributed to both the exploitation of the environment and the subjugation of women. Nature is presented as a living organism and its premodern perception of nature as a nurturing, organic entity after personified as 'mother earth'.

Main Text

According to her, scientific revolution, particularly the works of thinkers like Francis Bacon and Rene Descartes substituted this perspective with the mechanistic paradigm, treating nature as a machine to be controlled and exploited. She also draws a

resemblance between the dominance of nature and the oppression of women during the rise of modern science and industrial capitalism. This book criticises the reductionist extractive approaches that emerged during the scientific revolution, linking these methods to environmental degradation. This book re-evaluates human relationships with nature, advocating for a return to more holistic and sustainable ways of thinking and living.

Maria Mies's *Ecofeminism* is a ground breaking work and it is also co-authored by Vandana Shiva. It provides a deep exploitation of the intersections between patriarchy, capitalism and environmental degradation. It shows how women and nature are interconnected and stem from the same systems of dominance. This work focuses on the traditional roles of women in sustaining life, emphasising their intimate connection to natural processes. Women knowledge primarily is indigenous and rural context is shown to be central to sustainable practices and ecological balance. They also referred to links of colonization. They also hint in criticism on globalization for inequality, environmental degradation and cultural homogenisation. It also examines the patriarchal structure which shape these exploitative scientific and technological paradigms. They primarily advocate for a holistic, feminist approach to knowledge and science that values diversity and inter connectedness. This work initiates a new relationship between humans and nature, deep rooted in care, sustainability and respect. They advised a shift towards local economies, community based knowledge systems and participatory democracy.

Eco-feminism as Politics: Nature, Marx and the Postmodern by Ariel Salleh is a ground breaking work on eco-feminism. This work amalgamates ecofeminist theories, ecological concern, feminist perspectives and critiques of capitalist and postmodern ideologies. The book builds a connection between ecological feminism and political ecology. Here the author criticises the traditional Marxism for its anthropocentric focus and lack of attention to gender. She also points out the way capitalism exploits both human labour specially women's unpaid reproductive labour and natural resources, calling for an ecofeminist reanalysing of Marxist theory.

She also has challenged the post-modernist thought for its relativism and tendency to overlook material ecological realities. She also added to this perspective that the labour performed by women is less valuable in capitalist society. She argued that women and nature both are treated as cheap resources in patriarchal and capitalist frameworks. This book propagates an egalitarian and sustainable future.

This book is essential for those who are interested in essentials for those who are interested in ecofeminism, environmental justice and the interplay between feminism and political ecology.

Feminism and the Mystery of Nature was written by Val Plumwood in 1993. In this work the author has given the dualistic idea that separates humans from nature and aligns eco-feminism with border ecological and social justice movements. He explains how dualism such as - male/female, reason/ nature and human/ animal are central to the domination of both women and the natural world. This dualistic thinking is the root of environmental destruction and social inequality. She argues that western thoughts have historically placed reason associated with men above 'nature' which is associated with women and other marginalized groups justifying their exploitation.

This book links the dominance of women and nature, emphasising their shared treatment as 'resources' in the patriarchal and capitalist system. Plumwood critiques the way in which this logic also extends to other forms of oppression, such as racism and specism. She advocates and ecological rationality that recognises the interdependence of all life forms and rejects the hierarchical separation between humans and nature. This book argues for a re definition of ethics and philosophy that values care, empathy and reciprocity. She envisions a world that moves beyond dominion to embrace diversity and sustainability.

Rosemary Radford Ruether's *Gaia and God: An Ecofeminist Theory of Earth Healing* is a seminal work that amalgamates Eco-feminism with theology, examining the religious, cultural and historical roots of environmental destruction and social injustice. It explores the interplay between ecology and spirituality. It analyses traditional theologies that separate God from creation and justify the dominance of nature and women. It challenges dualistic thinking in theology that places spirit above matter and men above women.

The author develops an ecofeminist theology that emphasizes interconnectedness, mutuality and care for all life forms. She advocates for re-interpretation of religious traditions to support ecological and social justice. She also advocates for the integration of ecological awareness into spiritual practice and ethical living. This book is highly beneficial for the audience interested in Eco-feminism, environmental ethics, or the religion in shaping our relationship with nature.

New Wilderness And Man V. Nature

The book *The New Wilderness* by Diane Cook is regarded as the environmental novel of our times. It felt like a fatal blow. From the beginning it shows how nature and wilderness is not an escape but a force that shapes us as we shape it and not always in a good way. Here the term wilderness in the title of the book and as it is discussed in the text, "An unmistakable shadow of a path led towards the camp. It was hard to know if it was from the community's own impact, animals making their own animal trails, or a remnant of all the things the land had been before it became the wilderness state." (4)

As the story progresses we see that there are a few different definitions of wilderness in many different uncontrolled environments which include both external and internal. Diane Cook's wilderness state even so called nature is influenced and controlled by humans at every level. The cultural theorist Raymond Williams calls 'nature' the most complex word in the English language because of the ambiguities around it. Sometimes one can point out this term wilderness is a cultural invention. Which refers to how people seek out wilderness as some kind of escape from their everyday experience.

A few centuries back this Wilderness had different connotations which refers to the feeling of solace among nature. If one went into the wilderness it was never for rest and relaxation but a reckoning. In the first scene where the protagonist Bea gives birth to her stillborn daughter and bury her in a shallow grave that she knows that she will be captured by wild animals such as coyotes as soon as she steps away from it which says, "The coyotes pranced impatiently and linked her yellow teeth from a far low ridge, some foothills to come, she heard a joyless howl some watching Wolf had seen the carrion birds was signalling pray." (3)

In the text, the primary characters are the mother and daughter and their relationship. How the characters are responding to each other in the state of wilderness. This book comes under cli-fi which means climate fiction. This genre frequently includes science fiction and dystopian themes which is very much a part of the book. The characters here venture into this inhospitable world in the varyingly close and distant third company Bea and a young mother who has the impossible and inadvisable decision to join an experiment in the wilderness state in order to save her little daughter, Agnes from the wasted city, whose poisoned air has been killing her since the day she was born. Many volunteers and Bea is also part of an experiment allegedly intended to determine whether humans can exist in nature without destroying it. The community of which she is unwilling and pragmatically sceptical is faster to set precious implements, the cast iron, and the book that spells out the rules of their existence. Volunteers participants are not the scientist and experts her well-meaning partner Glen predicted volunteering for the experiment when he first found it. As one might expect of ordinary souls thrown into extraordinary strife. The community's politicking grows ever more self-serving and craven and as their existence is challenged by newcomers and the unravelling of the structures they were told to believe in their respective motivations further and further from a collective objective.

One of the most convincing concerns in the books is the sarcastic force of individualising and how these human tendency to destroy really is and how the hard wired urge to self-preserve erodes the possibility of fellowship and forward thinking. Above all she seems to ask, how will we respect one another once the climate crisis finally becomes the uncontested crucible of our time? The writer explores this question through these characters stormy and unstable relationships passing the narrative touch from mother to daughter about halfway through the book. One can see how the characters are growing in this polluted city and then with Agnes, a true nomad for whom the wilderness state has always been home. The text reveals the unease relation between mother and daughter as they navigate disparate understanding of self, belonging, society and each other is the beating heart of the novel. In the text *The New Wilderness*, "The baby emerged from the Bea the colour of a bruise. Bea burned the cord somewhere between them and uncoiled it from the girl's slight neck and through she knew it was useless, swept her daughter up into her hands, trapped on her soft chest and blew few shallow breaths into her slimy mouth." (1)

The book *The New Wilderness* by Diane Cook presents two different worlds such as - natural world and human world. The book also explores the impact of human activity on nature, the tension between preservation and exploitation. The book moreover, analyses how and to what extent a child is being protected by his mother in a chaotic world. The world out there has become intolerable to live because of the bad environmental impact the girl is going to die. From time immemorial the patriarchy is trying to exploit the vulnerable and that is quite apt from the text that how nature and women are exploited and correlated.

The relationship between gender, environmentalism and eco feminism can be explored through the novel's portrayal of female characters and their connections to the natural world. There are few symbols in the book that represent eco critical ideas which includes water, fire, animals, time, sound, plants etc. These symbols on the other hand enrich the narratives of the text. The story is set in a future where much of the world has been devastated by climate change and urbanization. The story follows a mother and her daughter as they join a group of living in a wild reserve.

The narrative delves into the challenges they face both from the harshness of their surroundings and the complexities of their relationship. The author here raises questions about the meaning of wilderness and the sacrifice made for survival. Content like this makes it a powerful commentary on contemporary ecological issues.

Here the author is explaining the bodily structure of the new born baby how she is behaving, how small and fragile her body parts are and how vulnerable this creature has become. This text also explains how she is taking care of the baby. How she is trying to protect the baby from these ferocious animals and this is very clear from the lines.

Now, the animals, who has sensed it were converging. In the sky a cyclone of buzzards lowered as if to check on the progress, then uplifted on a thermal. She heard the soft trend of Coyotes. They wave through the bloomy sage. A mother and three skinny kits appeared under jaggedly thrown shade. Bea heard whines easy from their impassive yawns. They would wait. (2)

It shows how these animals are trying to kill and create obstacles for the mother and daughter. The mother is trying her best to protect the child from the dangerous people near her. She tried to protect her baby from every way possible. The environment is this much toxic, no baby deserve to be born here. When the character is moving from one place to another what kinds of challenges she has faced which are very evident in the text.

This book stands out from other ecofeminist books for many reasons, particularly how it deals and approaches themes of nature, human survival and primarily the degradation of environment. This book explores the bond between Bea and her daughter Agnes against the backdrop of a collapsing world. The relationship is central to the narrative and implies as a way for examining human connection, sacrifice and survival in nature. While many eco feminist works explore women's role in ecological system.

The bond between mother and daughter adds an intimate depth to the story. The characters presented here are morally complex and flawed. The book challenges the notion that returning to nature is inherently redemptive, showing instead the harshness and brutality of Wilderness survival. The novel shows the bureaucratic system that manage the wilderness state as controlling and manipulative, offering a nuanced look at how power operates in environmental content. In this text motherhood is depicted with restless endurance and sacrifice. This presentation binds the experience of motherhood to the broader human struggle for survival in a degraded world, emphasising resilience over romanticized care giving. This is set to make it more focus on women with nature. One lacking quality of this book is it lacks action and agenda. This book focuses more and more on storytelling. It uses speculative fiction to refer ecofeminist themes, focusing on the complexities of human relationships, survival and environmental ethics in a very thought provoking manner.

Conclusion

The conclusion of this book is very ambiguous which dealt with the core themer of sacrifice, survival and human-nature relationship. After enduring many hardships in the wilderness state, the relationship between the mother and daughter reaches a breaking point. The daughter grown into an independent person who can handle this harshness in the wilderness. Here the character Bea is selfless sacrificing to give better chances of survival to others. The book ended with the point where the daughter Agnes is continuing her journey with the group to become a survivor in the wilderness.

In addition to this a story also portrays the struggle of the group as they navigate both internal conflicts and external threats from the wilderness itself. Cook's vivid description of the wild setting contrasts with the character's emotional landscape, creating a rich narrative that invites readers to reflect on their own connections to nature and the consequences of modern living. This work is vital and substantial for the audience interested in eco criticism. The book emphasizes the complex and cynical nature of life. The inevitable separation of parent and child and humanity's unpleasant relationship with nature. This work also challenges readers to contemplate the reading over to reflect on the cost of survival and the sacrifices required to protect the environment.

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